

SUSTAINABLE EFFECTS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN PROMOTING ACADEMIC LIBRARIES RESOURCES AND SERVICES IN EKANEM IKPI BRAIDE LIBRARY, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF LAFIA

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Library, Marketing, Information, Resources, services.

Abstract: *This article is focused on sustainable effects of marketing strategies in promoting academic libraries resources and services in Ekanem Ikpi Braide Library, Federal University of Lafia'. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. There is Introduction to the study. Problem statement, Objectives of the study include: 1. To identify the available information resources available in Federal University of Lafia Library. 2. To identify the methods used by Federal University of Lafia Library to market available information resources. 3. Suggest possible strategies for enhancing effective marketing of information resources and services in Federal University of Lafia Library. And three research questions which are in line with the objectives of the study. Literature review, concepts of reasons for marketing library resources and services. Research methodology, the population of the study was 53 of the entire library staff, instrument used for data collection was questionnaire with four points rating scale which is Strongly Agree =SA, Agree =A, Disagree =D, Strongly Disagree =SD. Method used for data collection done through the help of a colleague as research assistant and it was on the spot to avoid colossal loss. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics frequency distribution, mean, mode and median. Results of the study include: the presence of e-books received a highest mean score of 3.1 and the lowest mean score was the availability of indexes and abstracts (mean of 2.4) and conference proceedings (mean of 2.4) were seen as inadequate, suggesting that these areas need improvement to better meet the needs of library users. The second one addressed Strategies such as social media marketing (mean score of 2.8) and word of mouth (mean of 3.0) were acknowledged as effective tools. Additionally, the importance of staff training in marketing efforts (mean of 3.1) and the effectiveness of current marketing efforts. The*

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third question addressed various strategies that respondents believe would enhance marketing efforts at the library. Email marketing and newsletters received a mean score of 3.3, indicating strong support for this approach. Social media marketing (mean of 3.2) and collaborations with faculty (mean of 3.1) were also recommended as effective strategies. However, suggestions for improvement in the library's website and continuous adjustments to marketing strategies (both mean scores of 3.0) show that respondents are keen on ensuring that marketing efforts remain relevant and effective in reaching their audience. Part of the recommendation was that, library should focus on improving its social media presence and implementing email marketing campaigns to better engage users among others.

Introduction

Academic libraries as major organs are found in tertiary institutions such as universities, polytechnics, and colleges. They operate with modus operandi to achieve the institutions' objectives as specified (Aboh & Egbe, 2022). Information products and services are the ingredients and commodities involved in the study and practice of information science. That is why information science looks at the provision, accessibility and utilization of information. Libraries and information centres play essential roles in actualizing this mission of information science. Unfortunately, the information products and services offered by these libraries are sometimes not fully taken advantage of by information users, thereby calling for the adoption and use of marketing strategies in getting them across to those that need them. Marketing activities are seen as part of daily life. Most people view marketing as advertising, buying or selling or the exchange of goods and services. Marketing is much more beyond these.

Rather, it should incorporate an intersection between both parties with the focus of an exchange of value aimed at gaining something satisfying.

To serve both the academic library and its users, marketing seeks; to discover the needs and wants of prospective users and then to satisfy them. The key to achieving these two objectives is the idea of exchange, which is the trade of things of value between the library and user so that each is better off after trade. For marketing to occur in the academic library, at least four factors are required: two or more parties with unsatisfied need (i.e. the library and its users); a desire and ability to satisfy these needs; a way for both the library and it's users to communicate and something to exchange.

An organization that has a market orientation focuses its efforts on continuously collecting information about customers' needs, sharing this information across departments, and using it to create customer value. A recent focus in the customer relationship era has been the advent of

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social networking, in which organizations and their customers develop relationships through social media websites such as Facebook, Twitter(X), and YouTube, among others. This focus will allow libraries to understand and market to current and prospective customers in ways that are still evolving, such as in using social media. Library has limited human, financial, technological, and other resources available to market its services. Therefore, the library must develop strategies to help them focus and direct its effort to accomplish its goals. The library's foundation is its philosophical reason for being- why it exists. Successful libraries use this foundation to guide and inspire their employees through three elements: core values, mission, and organizational culture. To set a strategic direction the library needs to answer two difficult questions, where are we now? And where do we want to go? Asking the library means identifying its competencies, users and competitors.

Statement of the Problem

It is necessary for the library to be creative and innovative but it is also important that the library be able to sell the outcome of its creativity and innovation. The existence and survival of the library depend, to a large extent, on the ability of the library to get its products across to customers. One of the greatest needs of librarians and information specialists is to understand and develop marketing programs for their products and services. Modern marketing programs are built around the "marketing concept" and performance, which directs

managers to focus their efforts on, identifying, satisfying and following up the customer's needs: all at a profit.

One of the challenges facing libraries today is how to identify and satisfy information needs as peculiar to different users through exchange process. This particular challenge stresses the need for libraries to carefully draft information marketing plans which will complement the library's vision, mission and that prudent plan worked out by focusing on expected market trends always get good results. Marketing plans require a great amount of effort in terms of time, strategy and credibility. Devising marketing plans for the library involves collective efforts. It should be planned so that it boosts the profitability of the library.

It has been observed that marketing has not been explored fully in Federal University of Lafia (FULafia) main library. Therefore, it is necessary to study the marketing trends in FULafia library. The motivation is to raise awareness of the library and its services, and for the library to market its products in a way that attracts users. This study therefore seeks to investigate the effects of marketing strategies in promoting academic libraries in Federal University of Lafia Library, Lafia, Nasarawa State.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is predicated on the information dissemination on sustainable effects of marketing strategies in promoting academic libraries resources and services in

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Federal University of Lafia Library. The specific objectives are:

1. To identify the available information resources in Federal University of Lafia Library.
2. To identify the methods used by Federal University of Lafia Library to market available information resources.
3. Suggest possible strategies for enhancing effective marketing of information resources and services in Federal University of Lafia Library?

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. What are the available information resources in Federal University of Lafia Library?
2. What are the methods used by Federal University of Lafia Library to market available information resources?
3. What are the possible strategies for enhancing effective marketing of information resources and services in Federal University of Lafia Library?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing is generally aimed at attracting and retaining active and potential customers, while marketing library information resources and services includes all strategies used in projecting satisfactory services to users and also identify information needs of non-users. Kotler (1999), sees marketing as the process of planning and extending the concept of pricing, promotion and distribution of goods, and services with ideas to create exchanges with target groups that satisfy customers and organizational objectives. People

are the potential or actual users of the product while marketing is the action of advertising (creating awareness), and promoting the products for sell. Bhatt and Gupta (2018), divided the concept of marketing in library into four broad parts:

Marketing as a set of techniques: It refers to the application of various methods, tools, and strategies to achieve marketing objectives and promote products, services, or ideas (Kumar & Mirchandani, 2018). It is a toolkit; a set of practical techniques and proven process which can be applied to all aspects of the service planning, service delivery, and service evaluation. Effective service planning begins with market research, analysis of needs and preferences of the user community. Effective service delivery requires market awareness; a carefully planned strategy of promotional activity. Effective service evaluation needs to start with the market response, the views of users (and non-users), about service performance.

Marketing as a philosophy: Exploring the philosophical landscape in search of opportunities for marketing and management thought and in particular for new categories, reference points, research paradigms, and conceptual frameworks (Matteo & Francesco, 2021). The premise of marketing is simple and appealing as "the user or customer is the beginning and end of every library activity". The satisfaction of a customer is the primary concern of marketing and the entire ethos and shared values of the library owe the responsibility of

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satisfying the customer. Everyone in the library, from top to bottom has a role to play in rendering maximum satisfaction to the customer. As such the attitude of service providers becomes important.

Marketing as an approach: The marketing approach is an attitude of research, analysis, listening to the market and its' supposed environmental permit (Sfetcu, 2020). In libraries, marketing does not require the creation of a separate department and the appointment of a person to look after this department, but marketing is everyone's function from top management to the front lines, it is a total organizational effort. Inter-functional coordination and cross-cultural perspective become important in order to remove communication barriers, work in teams and empower the workforce.

Customer-driven marketing: Marketers want to reinforce and retain regular users, attract targeted non-users, and reinvigorate relationships with ex-users (Homburg & Pflesser, 2019). The role of marketing is more than finding customers for the available information sources, services and technologies. Among others, marketing forms a partnership with the user who becomes the central part of the total service efforts. It requires an in depth understanding, greater intimacy and mutual trust between the library and its users. This comes through increasing the benefits to users in relation to the efforts and costs.

The knowledge that the user is the centre of marketing concepts gives libraries and its management the orientation of providing enabling environment and exclusive services geared towards the interest of every user group. This will enhance the utilization of products and services. All the methods of marketing activities in relation to other organizations equally apply in the area of library information products and services. Academic libraries offer varied services to their users which include; reference services and the conventional services (Ike, Amadi, Madu-Malachy, Iheagwam & Iheanacho, 2023). The authors further stressed that the conventional services include; circulation (issue and return of books), reprography and inter-library loan services while reference services include current awareness services, selective dissemination of information service, information brokerage, community information service, user education, library display services, referral services, reference services: current awareness services, referral services, inter-library loan, library display/exhibition, user education, etc.

When libraries acquire quality information resources and provide quality services, a significant influence is usually seen on the users. Users will show satisfaction by coming back to the library to make use of such materials or services and also make the good of the library to others.

Concept of Reasons for Marketing Library Resources and Services

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Marketing of library resources and services is categorically important to academic library owing to the fact that it improves the image of the library, attract potential users and sustain existing/active users. It also helps librarians to update their knowledge on recent innovations and approach in their organization. Echem and Alex-Nmecha (2019), opined that there is no doubt, the marketing of library and information services is inevitable and there are encouraging factors as well as reasons justifying application of marketing principles to library services and information products. They added that it is a fact that librarianship is experiencing rapid change. The ever-changing technological innovation has changed library function and services. Various internal as well as external factors are reshaping the role of libraries.

The following factors according to Chandrate and Chandrate (2015), are responsible for encouraging the library profession to develop a marketing approach in its operations and services: the information explosion (rapid growth of reading materials), the technology revolution, escalating library costs/budget cuts, increase of user based service, networking demands/complexity in information requirements, reading habits among people declining due to reasons such as onslaught of television and internet. There is need for librarians to keep up with the positive pace with the increasing number of information users in the utilization of library resources and services are accelerating (Omini & Ayanlade, 2019). In

order to remain relevant in the competitive environment with some intruders in the business of information providers, library must take lead in web-based commercial services; libraries must market their services to the public to make strong connection with community of users (Onwuekwe, 2022).

Marketing of library resources and services enhances effective service delivery which in turn causes premium satisfaction to users. Marketing helps librarian ascertain exact needs of users which helps the library in decision making especially while library budget is been prepared in this era of stiffing finances. Furthermore, it fosters consciousness of the value of library usage and also will help the library generate income internally through offering services such photocopying, reprographic services, amongst other income generating services.

Concept of Marketing Mix: the 7Ps methods and Libraries

7Ps are foundations of marketing theory which are used for service marketing. These marketing variables allow libraries to use this services marketing mix. According to Echem and Alex-Nmecha (2019), the mission and objectives of libraries are modified in line with conditions, services, procedures, policies, rules and operation in line with the changes that occur with the marketing mix. This implies that in libraries and information centers, marketing plan and research should be put in place to help define the policies and promotional tools to reach a target group of potential library users. Marketing mix is

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the combination of several ideas and strategic plans by marketers or librarians in order to influence and promote the demand and utilization of its product or brand. It is an important tool that helps the library understand what their product or services can offer and how to plan for a successful product offering.

The marketing mix frequently described in terms of the combination of four major tools of marketing namely, product, price, place and promotion known widely as the 4Ps. The extended marketing mix adds people, physical evidence and process (7Ps). They further stressed that the applications of the marketing mix tools in marketing library information products and services are as follows:

Product: Product is anything that can be offered to the market to satisfy a need or want. The products to be marketed could be physical goods, services, persons, places, ideas, and companies. Library products are all the services offered by the library to satisfy the information needs of all that would desire such. These tangible and intangible product services include library lending, inter-library loan, online searching, abstracting and summaries, indexing bibliographic information, books, databases, journals, bulletins, films, audio recording, reference, document delivery, current content, selective dissemination of information SDI, current awareness, etc. as the product items. In the aspect of digital environment digital marketing mix that deals with creation and management of the digital product, e-product (e-

books, e-journals, online databases) features and benefits of products with new product development which satisfy the users need and desires resource product. The products have the greatest characteristics with contextual value, reproducibility, Interactivity, ability to repackaging, technological delivery, packaging, and branding (Gamit, Patel & Patel, 2021).

Place: Place is an important aspect of the four Ps. It tells where the products are sold (library space). Place here refer to a location of information and that of the user. There is need for a distribution channel, inventory, transportation etc. to make the information available from its location at the point of creation to its use by the user (Etukudo & Atanda 2023). It also indicates the channel through which the product is conveyed to the market (physical and virtual) and the location where the library is situated. This is very important because books displayed in strategic places like the shelves attract more current or potential users unlike those hidden. It is expected that a library building be located in strategic places that can easily be accessible to all users. Strategically located libraries attract the attention of potential and prospective users to its maximum utilization. Conversely, a hidden library irrespective of its rich collections or products and artificially designed will end up being underutilized.

Price: Pricing consists of both the time the library staff spends to ensure that library products and services are made available and

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accessible to satisfy the users within the possible shortest time space. How a product is priced will directly affect how it sells. Product always is seen as representing good value for investment, it defined the value obtained in exchange. It plays both economical and psychological perspectives crucial role. In the context of digital environment electronic resource pricing, pay for use, online subscription of database and other electronic resources (Gमित, Patel & Patel, 2021). Library clientele patronage usually depends on the provision, availability and accessibility of the relevant information products of all formats (books and non-books) that would be of value to them. For information products and services, the relevant terms may be price of a physical product like CD-ROM and library user registration fee, etc. Other information services that a library could offer for a fee covers "added value" services such as abstracting and indexing, inter-loan, photocopying, binding, SDI, database searches etc. To determine a price, it is necessary for librarians to clearly understand its role, impact and factors surrounding pricing and costing. Value of products and services varies depending on the situation and time of availability. However price could be determined depending on the prevailing situation in the library. This will include the level of revenue generation and profitability margin.

Promotion: Promotion is an important aspect of marketing. It stimulates demand for a product thereby enhancing sales. Promotion refers to marketing communication. In this process, the

marketer's goal is to communicate with users so that they recognized the product. Marketers must design strategies to persuade present and prospective customers to purchase their goods. The benefits gained from employing a service organization's services define the value and importance of promotion (Huzaifa & Sehar 2022).

It is an aspect of the market mix that involves libraries and librarians engaging the users or prospective patrons in communication in order to acknowledge the existence of the resources available, services and products offered by the library or information center or certain new library products. Library promotion is basically aimed at to select a method that can encourage the users to respond to utilizing the products. It is the medium librarians and information managers use to disseminate, publicize or create awareness of available library products and services that can be offered to their users and non-users and what they stand to gain from the library. Building clientele relationship, branding and repackaging of information resources, marketing library services, marketing strategy and planning are very fundamental to the promotion of library services.

People: People element of the marketing mix involves the contact staffs who are key players in promotion and marketing the library products through information services delivery, often creating and delivering the products in the interaction with the customer. The quality of the interaction between the service agent and the

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customer is a major influence on satisfaction (Ikolo, 2018). In library services, it is expected that every user needs to feel comfortable with the librarians, to trust them and to develop a rapport with them. Based on this, it is important that librarians and other library staff as image makers conduct themselves because the attitude and responsiveness of the staff will determine how users will perceive the service quality and its acceptability. Users can evaluate the service quality based on the attitude of the staff.

Physical Evidence: This refers to the physical environment in which the information products and services are delivered. This implies that the library structure should be in working condition and very appealing. The arrangement pattern should also be user friendly to suit various group users. Real quality of the service as perceived by a user could be judged by the physical attributes of the library. It refers to the environment and facilities that libraries need to provide services to its patrons. It also encompasses all tangible, visible touch points (the full environment) with which your customers/users will interact prior to acquire your services (Huzaifa & Sehar 2022). The physical evidence serves to reinforce patron's perception of the library image in terms of quality of service, value etc. Libraries, therefore, should design the physical evidences more carefully to ensure it represents the quality, value and the desired image to the users. This is necessary because it is a contributing factor to significant marketing concept image.

Process: Process consists of process, planning, control, operation planning, facilities to be available with users, scheduling, quality of services etc. These are the procedures, mechanisms and flow of activities by which the reference and information services are acquired to accomplish the achievement of quality services delivery to library users (Ikolo, 2018). It is important that librarians maintain due process and recognize the fact that users utilize the process characteristics as a form of evidence for judging the quality of service.

Strategies for Enhancing Marketing Library Resources and Services

Marketing strategy means selecting various techniques in proper proportion and balance. It is crucial for librarians to be well informed of various marketing tricks and be able to choose the appropriate ones required for its products and services in specific situations. A well-designed library web page is a good way of promoting library information services and resources, the emails containing the tips about finding information on library resources are of great value at the critical stage, use library wall space by displaying different language study tools such as bilingual dictionaries, English thesaurus, dictionary of synonyms and antonyms, subject-related dictionaries and encyclopedias, the librarian needs to meet the users to discuss and gather the relevant information they required, the libraries need to provide "Help" services link to library web pages,

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where assistance may be provided to search for resources (Mandrekar & Rodriguez, 2023).

In this new millennium, library website, email, web page, OPAC, online survey, online advertisements, social media platform can effectively serve as a tools used in promoting information product and services most especially in the library, while strategy including reaching out to the users through word of mouth by moving round the campus on a fixed day, visiting lecture hall, use of current awareness services, advertising in print media, pasting of new information on the notice board, internet advertising, social media advert, all these efforts put together will increase the level of library usage, and if properly manage will lead to effective service delivery and users satisfaction (Onwueke, 2022).

To cut cost in marketing library services and resources Kumar, (2017) listed the below promotional services which are cost effective, as they require little investment in resources and reach the intended patrons directly: digital media: library website, e-mail services, web page alert, library portal, OPAC, online survey, webcasts and web announcements, online advertising social network site such as Facebook, Twitter(X), Flickr, YouTube, Blogs, Wikis, RSS, Web 2.0; Print media: booklets, flyers, banner/posters, bookmarks, newspaper alert and newsletter, user statistics, library publications, annual calendar, feedback form, postcard/letters, survey; events and activities: workshops, seminars, user-education and

orientation, word of mouth, classroom instruction, face-to-face events, library tours, training session, one-to-one conversations.

Academic libraries can market their services and products using different social media platforms for exchanging, advertising their information resources through Facebook and WhatsApp. Advocacy is another strategy for library marketing which is achieved by building partnership with influential stakeholders, increasing academic library participation in community services, ensuring library faculty collaboration, and sharing library-faculty collaboration, and sharing library's testimonies (Alex-Nmecha & Igbinovia, 2020).

The challenges of underutilization being faced by most academic libraries in Nigeria can be solved by aggressive library marketing using the best tools and strategies as well as targeting the right audience with the right techniques (Madu & Ajayi, 2022). The authors in their work recommended that more funds should be allocated for marketing purposes by the management of the parent institutions; library management should expose the librarians to marketing trainings through conferences, seminars, workshop and symposia; librarians should be more committed to their work and introduce new techniques to market their library services, and the library management should develop a workable marketing policy to drive the concept of library marketing.

Other solutions as suggested by Gamit and Patel 2021, includes designing digital marketing

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strategies to provide efficient academic library services; focusing on selective resources that the academic library needs to promote; designing strong steps to face the competitors of all types library in the academic library; adopt modern technologies while using marketing strategy in academic library services; using simple language, which may communicate clear messages to academic library users through social media platforms; adopting digital marketing strategies based on the academic library budget; and getting feedbacks from the academic library users and working on it.

Madu, Aboyade and Aboyade 2023, concluded that effective and efficient engagement of library marketing by academic library managers, personnel, and all other relevant stakeholders has the potential to improve the declining level of library patronage as such advised that academic library managers and staff should continue to design and implement effective marketing strategies that could efficiently communicate the resources, services and facilities to the academic staff using relevant media and channel.

In view of the foregoing, Osinilu, Adekunmisi, Okewale, and Oyewusi 2018, in their study marketing strategies used by librarians in state university libraries recommended that the university management should encourage the use of ICT tools and applications to enable the university library and its branches to skilfully and innovatively market information resources, products and services. In the same vein, the university library should purchase more

computers, laptops, smart phones and other hand-held devices that will support the use of social media tools and services among library staff and users; user surveys or market research as marketing strategies should be carried out on a regular basis in order to continuously understand, identify and satisfy varying and changing information needs of patrons. An annual survey of the actual number of library users, identification of users' needs, nature and extent of use of the library, its resources and services, evaluation of existing services and products and development of new services and products could culminate into success of the library; and finally, the university library management should effectively utilize funding from the TETFund to purchase needed, highly relevant, current and quality print resources. The funds should also be utilized to purchase and install electronic facilities and web-based resources to facilitate effective use of social media tools and services by library staff and the university community.

Some other solutions to challenges facing marketing of library products and services include: need to encourage social media facilities use among library staff, facilitating job training in this direction for its library staff members as this would improve the level of relevance, awareness and encourage the usage of these social media facilities among the university library staff and university community at large by the university management; library personnel should fully apply social media to deliver

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information services as it helps them reach out to many people at a time as well as improve access to information services delivery; the library management should facilitate and encourage use of social media among library personnel by making available adequate infrastructure that supports internet connectivity in the library in other to resolved challenges encountered in usage of social media which will encourage the librarians and paraprofessionals to use the social media at work for library service delivery (Akinola, Zubairu & Saheed, 2022).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to gather data from academic library staff. Descriptive survey research is one that describes conditions as they exist naturally. This design is capable and efficient as it allows the researcher to analyze, interpret and state relationship between variables and provide accurate description of a particular situation. Descriptive survey research is crucial for studying effective marketing strategies for promoting academic libraries because it provides valuable insights into the current practices, challenges, and user needs (Kumar, Kumar and Patel, 2019).

Population of the study

The population for this study consists of all library staff members at Ekanem Ikpi Braide Library, Federal University of Lafia, totalling 53 individuals. This includes librarians, library

assistants, and other support staff who work directly with library operations.

Data Source: (Ekanem Ikpi Braide Library, 2024).

Sample and Sampling

Since the population size is relatively small, the entire population was used as the sample for the study. This will ensure that every library staff member has an equal opportunity to participate and provide their valuable insights. This is in line with Creswell's (1994) claim that in some cases, the entire population can be included in the study, especially when the population is small, easily accessible, and willing to participate.

Instrument for Data collection

A structured survey questionnaire on perceived effects of marketing strategies in promoting academic library's resources and services: a case study of Federal University of Lafia Library (PEMPALIRSFULQ) was used to collect data. The questionnaire consists of two sections. Section A contains demographic information about respondents while Section B contains five clusters that will focus on respondents' responses on research questions. Cluster 1 has 14 items; Cluster 2 has 11 items, Cluster 3 has 13 items, Cluster 4 has 10 items, while Cluster 5 has 12 items and a total of 60 items. The response keys are four-point Likert Scale Rating:

SA = Strongly Agree (4 point)

A = Agree (3 point)

D = Disagree (2 point)

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SD = Strongly Disagree (1 point)

Method of Data Collection

Data was collected by the researcher with the help of a colleague (research assistant) who was carefully selected, trained and briefed. The researcher and assistant were honest, sincere, hardworking, and impartial and possess technical competence including necessary practical experience. Face distribution of questionnaire was done and also collected on the spot.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics was used to analyze collected data. The measures included frequency

distribution which helps to understand response patterns, mean scores of each item to identify areas of strength and weakness, standard deviation, median and mode. Descriptive Statistics provides an overview of respondent’s attitudes and perceptions (Hair, Black, Babin and Anderson 2019).

Research Question 1: What are the available information resources in Federal University of Lafia Library?

Table 1 presents the responses on the availability of information resources at the Federal University of Lafia Library.

Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean (x̄)	n	Decision
1. There are adequate books in the library.	5	10	23	15	2.9	53	Agree
2. Journals are available in the library.	8	12	21	12	2.7	53	Agree
3. The library provides newspapers for users.	4	14	18	17	2.9	53	Agree
4. Magazines are available in the library.	6	15	20	12	2.7	53	Agree
5. Dictionaries are provided.	7	9	22	15	2.8	53	Agree
6. Indexes and abstracts are available.	9	12	17	15	2.4	53	Disagree
7. Encyclopedias are available in the library.	5	10	23	15	2.9	53	Agree
8. Online databases are accessible.	4	12	18	19	3.0	53	Agree
9. E-books are available.	3	9	21	20	3.1	53	Agree
10. The library provides online catalogs.	6	11	19	17	2.9	53	Agree
11. E-journals are available.	5	13	20	15	2.8	53	Agree
12. Theses and dissertations are accessible.	8	10	21	14	2.7	53	Agree
13. Open access resources are available.	5	8	19	21	3.1	53	Agree
14. Conference proceedings are available.	9	12	18	14	2.4	53	Disagree

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Table 1 show that respondents rated the availability of information resources in the library positively. Specifically, the presence of e-books received a mean score of 3.1, indicating a strong agreement regarding their availability. Similarly, online databases and open access resources both scored 3.0, reflecting a favorable perception among users. Other resources such as

adequate books and newspapers were also rated positively with mean scores of 2.9. However, the availability of indexes and abstracts (mean of 2.4) and conference proceedings (mean of 2.4) were seen as inadequate, suggesting that these areas need improvement to better meet the needs of library users.

Research Question 2: What marketing methods are used by Federal University of Lafia Library?

Table 2 shows the responses on marketing strategies employed by the library.

Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean (x̄)	n	Decision
1. The library uses social media for marketing.	6	11	22	14	2.8	53	Agree
2. Posters are used to promote library services.	5	14	20	14	2.7	53	Agree
3. The library sends emails for marketing.	7	10	23	13	2.8	53	Agree
4. Events are used as a marketing tool.	4	12	21	16	2.9	53	Agree
5. Word of mouth is a strategy used in marketing.	3	8	25	17	3.0	53	Agree
6. I participate in marketing activities.	9	15	16	13	2.3	53	Disagree
7. Marketing enhances service delivery.	3	9	20	21	3.1	53	Agree
8. Staff need professional and ICT skills for effective marketing.	2	7	23	21	3.1	53	Agree
9. Marketing attracts and retains potential users.	5	10	18	20	3.0	53	Agree
10. Current marketing efforts are effective.	6	12	19	16	2.8	53	Agree
11. There has been an increase in library usage due to marketing efforts.	7	9	18	19	2.9	53	Agree

Table 2 indicates that various marketing strategies employed by the library are perceived positively by the respondents. Strategies such as social media marketing (mean score of 2.8) and word of mouth (mean of 3.0) were acknowledged

as effective tools. Additionally, the importance of staff training in marketing efforts (mean of 3.1) and the effectiveness of current marketing efforts (mean of 2.8) were also highlighted. Nevertheless, participation in marketing

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activities received a lower mean score of 2.3, suggesting that there is a need to engage more library staff in these initiatives to enhance their effectiveness.

Research Question 3: What are the possible Strategies can be adopted to enhance effective marketing of resources and services in Federal University of Lafia Library?

Table 3 presents various strategies suggested by respondents to enhance the marketing of library resources at the Federal University of Lafia Library

S/N	Suggested Strategies	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	N	Decision
1	Social Media marketing	3	6	20	24	3.2	53	Agree
2	Email marketing and newsletters	2	7	18	26	3.3	53	Agree
3	Library website optimization and redesign	4	5	23	21	3.1	53	Agree
4	Events and exhibition	4	8	19	22	3.1	53	Agree
5	Collaborations with faculty and students	4	8	19	22	3.1	53	Agree
6	Partnership with student associations	3	7	22	21	3.1	53	Agree
7	Staff training and development	3	7	22	21	3.1	53	Agree
8	Employee recognition and awards	4	8	20	21	3.0	53	Agree
9	Collaborations with other academic libraries	4	6	21	22	3.1	53	Agree
10	Marketing strategy reviews and updates	3	7	20	23	3.0	53	Agree
11	Continuous improvement and adjustment	3	8	19	23	3.0	53	Agree

Table 3 suggests various strategies that respondents believe would enhance marketing efforts at the library. Email marketing and newsletters received a mean score of 3.3, indicating strong support for this approach. Social media marketing (mean of 3.2) and collaborations with faculty (mean of 3.1) were also recommended as effective strategies. However, suggestions for improvement in the

library's website and continuous adjustments to marketing strategies (both mean scores of 3.0) show that respondents are keen on ensuring that marketing efforts remain relevant and effective in reaching their audience.

Summary of Major Findings

Based on the analysis of data, the following findings emerged:

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1. First, regarding the availability of information resources, respondents generally agreed that the library offers a sufficient range of materials, including adequate books, journals, newspapers, and e-books, with mean scores ranging from 2.7 to 3.1. Notably, online databases and open access resources also received favourable ratings, both scoring a mean of 3.0. However, the availability of indexes and abstracts, as well as conference proceedings, was perceived as inadequate, with mean scores of 2.4, indicating an area that requires improvement.

2. In terms of marketing strategies, the library was found to utilize a variety of approaches effectively, such as social media and word of mouth, which received mean scores of 2.8 and 3.0, respectively. The necessity for staff training in marketing efforts was highlighted, achieving a mean score of 3.1, alongside the overall effectiveness of current marketing initiatives. However, participation in marketing activities scored lower at 2.3, suggesting a need for greater involvement of library staff.

3. Finally, the study suggested various strategies to enhance marketing effectiveness, including email marketing and newsletters,

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which received the highest mean score of 3.3, followed by social media marketing at 3.2 and collaborations with faculty and students, both scoring 3.1. There was also a consensus on the importance of continuously improving and adjusting marketing strategies, as indicated by a mean score of 3.0. These findings offer valuable insights into the current state of the Federal University of Lafia Library's resources, services, and marketing strategies, highlighting areas that necessitate further attention and improvement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The library should focus on improving its social media presence and implementing email marketing campaigns to better engage users.
2. Regular training sessions should be organized to equip library staff with the skills necessary for effective marketing and user engagement.
3. The library should work on increasing the availability of indexes, abstracts, and conference proceedings, as these areas were identified as needing improvement

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